

Unofficial Guide for ESLEs in the Emergency Department¹

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This document may be used as an inventory for the expectations of a trainee undergoing an Extended Supervised Learning Event (ESLE) in the Emergency Department.

At the start of the ESLE

The trainee introduces themselves to the outgoing area lead, and explains their role during the ESLE.

The trainee takes a clinical and situational handover from the outgoing area lead.

The trainee engages with the handover such that the handover is safe and effective.

The trainee uses a systematic, robust, safe and effective way of recording handover information and pending tasks, and is able to explain their system's strengths and weaknesses.***

The trainee uses the electronic dashboard to gain situation awareness of the area.

The trainee ensures the electronic dashboard is updated, so that it is a highly accurate reflection of the area.

The trainee is able to "read" the electronic dashboard, and to explain their understanding of the area based on it.***

The trainee identifies members of their team, and introduces themselves.

The trainee determines the team members' seniority and skill-mix.

The trainee is able to identify immediate opportunities, risks, and priorities.***

The trainee introduces themselves and their role to the nurse in charge of the area.

The trainee engages in a clinical huddle with the nurse in charge, to share awareness of the area, to identify risks, and to optimise patient care.

During the ESLE

The trainee provides senior clinical leadership to patients seen by members of the team.

The trainee tailors each clinical discussion to the needs of the patient and the team member, and is able to explain their decision-making around this – for example, which patients need to be physically reviewed.***

The trainee demonstrates familiarity with the Emergency Department's clinical policies, guidelines, protocols and pathways, and ensures that patients receive care in accordance with them.

The trainee follows-up on decisions that have been taken.

The trainee demonstrates leadership qualities, attitudes, and behaviours appropriate to their seniority.

¹ Based on: RCEM Curriculum, 'Kaizen Assessment Forms - A Practical Guide for Trainees, Supervisors and Users of RCEM ePortfolio Kaizen', Royal College of Emergency Medicine, 2021, <https://rcemcurriculum.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Kaizen-Assessment-Forms.pdf> & <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19339817>.

*** Prompt for assessor to question the trainee.

The trainee is able to demonstrate a flexibility and variation in their leadership skills, in response to changing situations.

The trainee ensures breaks for team members are allocated and taken.

The trainee uses opportunities for teaching team members.

The trainee responds appropriately to clinical demands in the area.

The trainee keeps the electronic dashboard updated in real-time.

The trainee demonstrates techniques to manage the pace of patients being seen, and decisions being made.***

The multi-disciplinary team members find the trainee to be approachable, trustworthy, and credible.

The trainee's oral communication is of a high standard.

The trainee's written notes are of a high medico-legal standard.

The trainee engages in clinical huddles with the nurse in charge, to share awareness of the area, to identify risks, and to optimise patient care.

The trainee maintains situational awareness of the area at all times, and is able to explain their techniques to achieve this.***

The trainee is able to identify immediate opportunities, risks, and priorities.***

In the Emergency Room (ER)

The trainee maintains an awareness of all red calls.

The trainee engages with the nurse in charge in assessing new patients, and any decision-making in relation to this.***

The trainee engages with team members from other areas regarding patients which need to come to the ER.***

The trainee demonstrates resuscitation team leadership in accordance with their seniority.

The trainee gives an appropriate handover of patients stepping down from the ER.

At the end of the ESLE

The trainee gives a clinical and situational handover to the incoming area lead.

The trainee ensures that the incoming area lead is satisfied the handover.

The trainee is able to identify and handover immediate opportunities, risks, and priorities.***

The trainee thanks team members and offers any support that may be required.

The trainee is able to constructively reflect on the strengths and weaknesses of their ESLE, and formulate a development plan.

Document information

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